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**MASTER'S PHOTO ART PROJECT
'ETHNIC LANGUAGE OF THE SACRED'****Oleksandr Bezruchko^{1a}, Volodymyr Bardyn^{2b}**

¹ Doctor of Study of Art, PhD in Cinematographic Art, Television, Professor;
e-mail: oleksandr_bezruchko@ukr.net; ORCID: 0000-0001-8360-9388

² Master's Student at the Cinema and Television Arts Department;
e-mail: bardun@ukr.net; ORCID: 0000-0002-6711-1317

^a Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts, Kyiv, Ukraine

^b Kyiv University of Culture, Kyiv, Ukraine

**МАГІСТЕРСЬКИЙ ФОТОМИСТЕЦЬКИЙ ПРОЄКТ
«ЕТНІЧНА МОВА САКРАЛЬНОГО»****Олександр Безручко^{1a}, Володимир Бардин^{2b}**

¹ доктор мистецтвознавства, професор;
e-mail: oleksandr_bezruchko@ukr.net; ORCID: 0000-0001-8360-9388

² магістрант кафедри кіно-, телемистецтва;
e-mail: bardun@ukr.net; ORCID: 0000-0002-6711-1317

^a Київський національний університет культури і мистецтв, Київ, Україна

^b Київський університет культури, Київ, Україна

**МАГИСТЕРСКИЙ ФОТОХУДОЖЕСТВЕННЫЙ ПРОЕКТ
«ЭТНИЧЕСКИЙ ЯЗЫК САКРАЛЬНОГО»****Александр Безручко^{1a}, Владимир Бардин^{2b}**

¹ доктор искусствоведения, профессор;
e-mail: oleksandr_bezruchko@ukr.net; ORCID: 0000-0001-8360-9388

² магистрант кафедры кино-, телеискусства;
e-mail: bardun@ukr.net; ORCID: 0000-0002-6711-1317

^a Киевский национальный университет культуры и искусств, Киев, Украина

^b Киевский университет культуры, Киев, Украина

Master's photographic art project 'Ethnic language of the sacred'

The author's idea of this master's photographic art project was to create a series of photographs that should draw attention to the current state of the sacred heritage of Boykivshchyna with the aim of their future preservation.

The series of works consists of photographs that convey archaic architecture, a special style of icon painting, church objects, carvings and interior paintings that are typical of the Boyko ethnos.

Photo No. 1. 'Crossroads'

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Camera / Lens / Tripod

Nikon D7200 /
Nikon AF-S NIKKOR 18-135mm 1:3.5-5.6G /
Velbon Super Ace II

Settings:

18 mm | F3.5 | ISO 500 | 1/3 s

Light scheme

Light source: light from windows.
Lighting: natural, warm, hard.

Light scheme for taking photograph № 1 called 'Crossroads' in Adobe Lightroom Classic CC:

- Exposure: +0,11.
- Contrast: +7.
- Shadows: +22.
- Blacks +23.
- Clarity: +24.
- Vibrance: +20.
- Saturation: +15.
- Noise Reduction: +40.
- Colour Noise Reduction: +45.
- Vignetting: -20.
- Removal of unnecessary elements.

Gluing images to create a 3D panorama of the photograph № 1 called 'Crossroads' in Image Composite Editor:

- Import (downloading of all necessary images).
- Stitch (setting of the required geometry for gluing, leveling the horizon).
- Crop (adjustment of the panorama size).
- Export (choice of format and quality).

Creating a 3D tour of the photograph № 1 called 'Crossroads' in Kolor Panotour Pro:

- Tour (downloading of a 3D panorama).
- Style (setting of a 3D tour style).
- Build (setting and outputting of a 3D tour).

The author's idea of the photograph №1. The Brick churches in Boykivshchyna were usually built in the form of a cross with one quadrangular or octagonal cupola above the intersection of the main nave and the transverse nave better known as transept. This photo was taken in the form of a 3D panorama to show the intersection called the middle cross and the branches from it that form the likeness of a cross. The technology of creation of a 3D panorama is to create a series of consecutive photographs that convey everything around. When shooting, the camera should be placed on a tripod so that the optical centre of a camera stays immovable when turning a tripod head. All photographs are taken with the same settings and with a 2/3 frame offset relative to each other.

Photo No. 2. 'Support'

Camera / Lens / Tripod

Nikon D7200 /
Nikon AF-S NIKKOR 18-135mm 1:3.5-5.6G /
Velbon Super Ace II

Settings:

18 mm | F4.5 | ISO 100 | 1/2 s

Light scheme

Light source: Light from windows.
Lighting: natural, cold, soft.

**Light scheme for taking
photograph № 2 called 'Support'
in Adobe Lightroom Classic CC:**

- Exposure: +0,05.
- Contrast: +7.
- Highlights: -30.
- Shadows: +20.
- White: -25.
- Blacks +21.
- Clarity: +25.
- Vibrance: +20.
- Saturation: +15.
- Noise Reduction: +40.
- Color Noise Reduction: +45.
- Removal of unnecessary elements.

**Gluing images to create a 3D panorama
of the photograph № 2
in Image Composite Editor:**

- Import (downloading of all necessary images).
- Stitch (setting of the required geometry for gluing, leveling the horizon).
- Crop (adjustment of the panorama size).
- Export (choice of format and quality).

**Creating a 3D tour of the photograph № 2
called 'Support' in Kolor Panotour Pro:**

- Tour (downloading of a 3D panorama).
- Style (setting of a 3D tour style).
- Build (setting and outputting of a 3D tour).

The author's idea of the photograph №2. For many Christians, the church is spiritual support. Accordingly, in the photograph are shown wooden beams, special supports that hold the central dome of a temple from the inside and prevent storms from breaking it. And a church is also a kind of pillar that morally supports a person from the inside and protects them from the hardships of life.

Photo No. 3. 'Two parts'**Camera / Lens / Tripod**

Nikon D7200 /
Nikon AF-S NIKKOR 18-135mm 1:3.5-5.6G /
Velbon Super Ace II

Settings:

18 mm | F3.5 | ISO 200 | 1 s

Light scheme

Light source: LED lamps, window light.
Lighting: combined.

Light scheme for taking photograph № 3 called 'Two parts' in Adobe Lightroom Classic CC:

- Exposure: +0,01.
- Contrast: +5.
- Highlights: -25.
- Shadows: +21.
- White: -25.
- Blacks +25.
- Clarity: +25.
- Vibrance: +20.
- Saturation: +15.
- Noise Reduction: +40.
- Color Noise Reduction: +45.
- Removal of unnecessary elements.

Gluing images to create a 3D panorama of the photograph № 3 in Image Composite Editor:

- Import (downloading of all necessary images).
- Stitch (setting of the required geometry for gluing, leveling the horizon).
- Crop (adjustment of the panorama size).
- Export (choice of format and quality).

Creating a 3D tour of the photograph № 3 called 'Two parts' in Kolor Panotour Pro:

- Tour (downloading of a 3D panorama).
- Style (setting of a 3D tour style).
- Build (setting and outputting of a 3D tour).

The author's idea of the photograph №3. Although the Boyko churches are three-part only two parts 'babynets' and nave are for the worshippers. Babynets comes from the Ukrainian word 'baba'(woman) and is situated on the west side. Women usually stood there. Above it could be choirs and in older buildings a chapel or a bell tower. The nave is the central and the largest part of a temple topped by a dome.

Photo No. 4. 'Sacral complex'

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Camera / Lens

Nikon D7200 /
AF-S NIKKOR 18-135mm 1:3.5-5.6G

Settings:

31 mm | F4 | ISO 250 | 1/800 s

Light scheme

Light source: the sun.

Lighting: natural, warm, hard.

**Editing the photo image № 4
called 'Sacral complex'
in Adobe Photoshop:**

- Exposure: +0,02.
- Contrast: +19.
- Highlights: -25.
- Shadows: +1.
- White: -71.

- Blacks +16.
- Clarity: +22.
- Vibrance: +20.
- Saturation: +15.
- Noise Reduction: +40.
- Color Noise Reduction: +45.
- Vignetting: -20.

The author's idea of the photograph №4. The Boykos had not only a temple. There was a bell tower next to it. Technical rooms could also be attached to a church. There was also a cemetery nearby and if necessary a priesthood could be created. It all formed a whole complex.

Photo No. 5. 'God's vineyard'

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Camera / Lens

Nikon D7200 /

Nikon AF-S NIKKOR 18-135mm 1:3.5-5.6G

Settings (Church):

24 mm | F3.8 | ISO 1250 | 1/1000 s

Settings (Sky):

135 mm | F5.6 | ISO 200 | 1/60 s

Light scheme

Light source: the sun.

Lighting: natural, warm, soft.

**Editing the photo image № 5
called 'God's vineyard'
in Adobe Photoshop:**

- Contrast: +25.
- Highlights: -99.
- Shadows: +9.
- White: -63.
- Blacks -13.
- Clarity: +19.
- Vibrance: +30.
- Saturation: +20.
- Noise Reduction: +40.

- Color Noise Reduction: +45.
- Vignetting: -20.
- Merge 2 photos into one.
- Comparison.
- Transformation.
- Eraser the areas of the sky that cover the church with an eraser.

The author's idea of the photograph №5. Floral ornament on a fence of a temple evokes an association with a vineyard from the Parable of the Wicked Workers in the Vineyard told by Jesus. Christ addressed this story to the Pharisees considering them to be evil workers in the vineyard. However, the parable ends with the landlord's return to replace the workers in the vineyard, and new vineyard workers are priests working on imaginary vineyards.

